

CULTURAL SCIENCES

ENCHANTING SCREENS: THE CULTURAL RESONANCE AND MYSTICAL APPEAL OF "PSYCHIC CHALLENGE" IN THE RUSSIAN-SPEAKING MEDIA AND TV SPACE

Panasiuk M.

*MA in Cultural Studies
Independent researcher,
Ukraine*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884390>

Abstract

This article delves into the phenomenon of the "Psychic Challenge" television show in modern-day Russian-speaking and cultural space, where it has achieved extraordinary popularity. It examines the cultural, historical, and social factors contributing to its success, tracing Russia's deep-rooted history of mysticism and folklore. Key historical figures such as Helena Blavatskaya, George Gurdjieff, and Nicholas Roerich are explored for their influence on contemporary Russian spiritualism. The article also highlights the high-value production of the show, its incorporation of Slavic magic and local cultures, and the impact of European and American cultural imports. Additionally, the resurgence of subcultures like gothic and emo, the appeal of archetypal figures, and the creation of alternative communities are discussed. This study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of why shows like "Psychic Challenge" resonate so profoundly with Russian-speaking audiences today.

Keywords: Psychic Challenge; Russian mysticism; Blavatskaya; Gurdjieff; Roerich; Cultural imports; Gothic subculture; Jungian archetypes; Alternative lifestyles.

Introduction

Overview of the Popularity of "Psychic Challenge" in Russian-speaking cultural space

"Psychic Challenge" (Битва экстрасенсов), a television show that features psychics and mediums competing to demonstrate their paranormal abilities, has become a cultural phenomenon in modern-day Russian-speaking cultural space. Since its debut, the show has consistently attracted a massive viewership, making it one of the most watched programs in the country (Mediascope, n.d.). This popularity is not merely a fleeting trend but rather a reflection of deeper cultural, historical, and social undercurrents in Russian-speaking society.

The show's format, which combines elements of reality TV with the mystique of supernatural abilities, resonates deeply with Russian-speaking audiences. Contestants are put through a series of tests designed to showcase their purported psychic powers, from locating hidden objects to diagnosing ailments. The dramatic flair and emotional intensity of these challenges captivate viewers, who are both skeptical and fascinated by the possibility of the paranormal. The show's high production values, compelling narratives, and charismatic participants contribute to its widespread appeal.

Purpose and Significance of the Study

This study aims to delve into the reasons behind the extraordinary success of "Psychic Challenge" in Russian media space. By examining the cultural, historical, and social factors at play, this research seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of why such a show resonates so profoundly with Russian-speaking audiences today.

One key aspect of this phenomenon is Russia's deep-rooted history of mysticism and folklore. From ancient Slavic traditions to the influence of prominent

mystical figures like Helena Blavatskaya (see Blavatsky, 1977, 1997), George Gurdjieff (1950; 1991), and Nicholas Roerich (2017a, 2017b, 2017c), the Russian spiritual landscape is rich and varied. These historical figures and their teachings have left a lasting impact on Russian culture, creating a fertile ground for the acceptance and fascination with the supernatural.

Additionally, the show's incorporation of Slavic magic and local cultures taps into a sense of national identity and heritage. The use of traditional symbols, rituals, and narratives not only entertains but also evokes a sense of nostalgia and connection to the past. This cultural resonance is further amplified by the influence of European and American cultural imports, which have introduced new dimensions to the Russian spiritual and entertainment landscapes.

The resurgence of subcultures like gothic and emo in Russian-speaking space also plays a role in the show's popularity. These subcultures, with their affinity for the mysterious and the macabre, find a kindred spirit in "Psychic Challenge." The show offers a platform for alternative lifestyles and communities, providing a space where unconventional beliefs and practices can be explored and validated.

Moreover, the appeal of archetypal figures—heroes, villains, mentors—within the show aligns with Carl Jung's theories of the collective unconscious (Jung, 2014). These figures tap into universal themes and emotions, making the show not only a form of entertainment but also a medium for exploring deeper psychological and existential questions.

In summary, "Psychic Challenge" is more than just a television show; it is a cultural phenomenon that reflects and influences contemporary Russian-speaking society and cultural space. By examining the historical roots, cultural significance, and social dynamics that contribute to its popularity, this study aims to shed light

on the broader implications of the show's success. Through this exploration, we can gain a deeper understanding of the ways in which entertainment, spirituality, and identity intersect in modern Russian-speaking cultural and media space.

Chapter 2: Historical Context

Russia's History of Mysticism and Folklore

Russia has a long and intricate history of mysticism and folklore that has profoundly shaped its cultural and spiritual landscape. The roots of Russian mysticism can be traced back to ancient Slavic pagan traditions, where nature worship and shamanistic practices were prevalent (Cvetkovic, 2021; Dixon-Kennedy, 1998). These early beliefs and rituals laid the groundwork for a rich tapestry of folklore that continues to influence Russian cultural space today.

Slavic mythology is filled with a pantheon of gods, spirits, and supernatural beings that reflect the natural and spiritual worlds. Figures such as Domovoi (household spirits), Leshy (forest spirits), and Baba Yaga (a witch-like figure) are deeply embedded in the collective consciousness (see Propp, 1968, 1984, 2012). These entities were believed to interact with humans, guiding and protecting them, or, in some cases, causing harm. The oral tradition of storytelling preserved these myths, passing them down through generations and embedding them in the cultural fabric of Russia.

The arrival of Christianity in Russian territory in the 10th century introduced new spiritual dimensions while simultaneously intertwining with existing pagan beliefs. The Russian Orthodox Church absorbed and adapted many pagan elements, creating a unique syncretism that blended Christian and pre-Christian practices. Icons, relics, and the veneration of saints became central to Russian spirituality (Fedotov, 1948), often coexisting with older, folkloric traditions (see Cvetkovic, 2021; Dixon-Kennedy, 1998; Helvin, 2019; and McIntosh, 2022).

The mystical aspect of Russian spirituality was further enriched by the advent of theosophy and other esoteric movements in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Theosophy, which sought to explore the divine wisdom underlying all religions, found a significant following in Russian-speaking space (Blavatsky 1977, 1997), laying the groundwork for the later popularity of psychic phenomena and supernatural themes in Russian-speaking media.

Influence of Notable Figures: Helena Blavatskaya, George Gurdjieff, and Nicholas Roerich

Helena Blavatskaya

Helena Blavatskaya, a key figure in the theosophical movement, was instrumental in shaping Russian and global interest in mysticism. Born in 1831 in Yekaterinoslav (now Dnipro, Ukraine), Blavatskaya co-founded the Theosophical Society in 1875. Her works, including "Isis Unveiled" (1877) and "The Secret Doctrine" (1888), synthesized elements of Eastern and Western spiritual traditions, promoting a vision of universal spiritual truth (Blavatsky, 1977, 1997). Blavatskaya's teachings emphasized the interconnectedness of all life and the potential for human spiritual evolution,

ideas that resonate with contemporary interest in psychic phenomena and spiritual exploration (Blavatsky, 1977).

Helena Petrovna Blavatskaya, co-founder of the Theosophical Society in 1875, is a pivotal figure in the history of Russian mysticism. Blavatskaya's work, particularly her seminal texts "Isis Unveiled" and "The Secret Doctrine," synthesized elements of Eastern and Western esoteric traditions (Blavatsky, 1977, 1997). Her teachings emphasized the existence of an ancient wisdom tradition that transcended cultural and religious boundaries.

Blavatskaya's influence extended beyond the Theosophical Society, inspiring a generation of spiritual seekers and esoteric scholars in Russia and around the world. Her ideas about the interconnectedness of all life and the hidden dimensions of reality resonated deeply with those disillusioned by the materialism and dogmatism of the 19th century. According to Goodrick-Clarke (2004),

"The corresponding influence of Blavatsky on twentieth-century esoteric movements has been prolific, confirming her status as a foremother of New Age spirituality in our own time." (Goodrick-Clarke, 2004: 9–10).

George Gurdjieff

George Gurdjieff, another influential figure, contributed significantly to the development of modern esoteric thought. Born in the Caucasus region in the late 19th century, Gurdjieff's teachings focused on the concept of self-awareness and the pursuit of spiritual enlightenment through disciplined practice. His seminal work, "Beelzebub's Tales to His Grandson" (1950), presents a complex cosmology and a call for individual awakening. Gurdjieff's emphasis on personal transformation and the exploration of higher states of consciousness has had a lasting impact on Russian and global spiritual communities (Gurdjieff, 1950).

George Ivanovich Gurdjieff, a contemporary of Blavatskaya, further expanded the landscape of Russian mysticism with his teachings on human consciousness and spiritual development. Gurdjieff's system, often referred to as the Fourth Way, emphasized self-awareness, inner transformation, and the integration of body, mind, and spirit. His book "Meetings with Remarkable Men" (1991) and his collaboration with the French philosopher P.D. Ouspensky brought his ideas to a broader audience (Gurdjieff, 1991; Lachman, 2006).

Gurdjieff's influence is evident in the emphasis on personal spiritual practice and the quest for higher knowledge that permeates contemporary Russian spiritualism. His teachings encouraged a pragmatic approach to mysticism, focusing on practical exercises and self-discipline. As Lipsey (2019) notes, Gurdjieff's "methods and behavior come from the fact that he worked at the same time on our two natures." (Lipsey, 2019: 40).

Nicholas Roerich

Nicholas Roerich, an artist, philosopher, and explorer, is another key figure in the development of Russian mysticism. Roerich's extensive travels in Central Asia and his encounters with Eastern spiritual traditions

profoundly shaped his worldview (Roerich, 2017b). His artistic works, infused with spiritual symbolism, and his philosophical writings, particularly the Agni Yoga series, contributed to a renaissance of mystical thought in Russia.

Nicholas Roerich, an artist, philosopher, and explorer, further enriched the Russian mystical tradition. His expeditions to Central Asia and his extensive body of artwork and writings reflect a deep engagement with spiritual themes (Roerich, 2017b, 2017c). Roerich's promotion of the Agni Yoga teachings, which advocate for the harmonious integration of spiritual and material life, has influenced many spiritual seekers in Russia and beyond. His vision of a spiritually united humanity resonates with the themes of interconnectedness and higher consciousness that are central to the appeal of shows like "Psychic Challenge" (Roerich, 2017a, 2017b, 2017c).

Roerich's vision of a unified spiritual culture that transcended national and religious boundaries resonated with many in Russia and beyond. His establishment of the Roerich Pact, an international treaty for the protection of cultural heritage, highlighted his commitment to the preservation and promotion of spiritual and cultural values. According to Andreyev (2014), Roerich and his colleagues' "ultimate purpose was to span a "cultural bridge" between Russia and India" (Andreyev, 2014: 429).

Chapter 3: The Show's Production

Analysis of the High-Value Production Elements

"Psychic Challenge" is renowned for its high production values, which play a crucial role in its appeal and success. The show's polished presentation, dramatic pacing, and professional cinematography set it apart from other reality TV programs. The careful curation of challenges, the compelling personal stories of contestants, and the atmospheric settings contribute to a captivating viewing experience (Turner, 2010a: 14–15).

The production team employs a variety of techniques to enhance the show's mystique and suspense. High-quality camera work and editing create a sense of immediacy and intimacy, drawing viewers into the narrative. The use of special effects, such as dramatic lighting and soundscapes, heightens the tension and underscores the supernatural themes. According to Mokhov (2016),

"I am proceeding from the premise that this show is a game show in terms of plot and is filmed from a pre-written script. Thus, the plots are constructed and represent specific narratives that can be categorized within the framework of the concepts of symbolic immortality described above." (Mokhov, 2016: 36).

Analysis of the High-Value Production Elements

"Psychic Challenge" stands out not only for its captivating content but also for its high production values, which significantly contribute to its success. The show's creators have invested heavily in ensuring that each episode is visually appealing, emotionally engaging, and technically sophisticated.

Visual and Technical Excellence

The production quality of "Psychic Challenge" is evident in its use of high-definition cameras, sophisticated editing techniques, and dramatic lighting and sound effects. These elements work together to create a visually immersive experience that draws viewers into the world of the contestants and their psychic challenges. The use of slow-motion sequences, close-up shots, and atmospheric music heightens the tension and drama, making each psychic demonstration feel momentous and compelling.

Storytelling and Emotional Engagement

The show's narrative structure is another key element of its production success. Each episode is carefully crafted to build suspense and maintain viewer interest. The personal stories of the contestants, their emotional journeys, and the reactions of the audience and judges are all woven together to create a compelling narrative arc. This focus on storytelling helps to humanize the contestants, making their psychic abilities feel more relatable and authentic (Turner, 2010a: 27–29).

Expert Commentary and Skepticism

To enhance credibility, "Psychic Challenge" features commentary from experts in various fields, including psychology, parapsychology, and magic. These experts provide insights into the contestants' abilities, offering both supportive and skeptical perspectives. This balanced approach not only adds depth to the show but also engages a wider audience, including those who may be skeptical of psychic phenomena.

Integration of Slavic Magic and Local Cultural Elements

One of the distinguishing features of "Psychic Challenge" is its integration of Slavic magic and local cultural elements. The show frequently incorporates traditional rituals, symbols, and folklore, creating a sense of authenticity and cultural resonance. This integration not only entertains but also educates viewers about Russia's culturally rich spiritual heritage (see Cvetkovic, 2021; Dixon-Kennedy, 1998; Helvin, 2019; and Mcintosh, 2022).

Challenges often draw on elements of Slavic magic, such as the use of amulets, divination techniques, and traditional healing practices. These elements are presented with a reverence for their historical and cultural significance, emphasizing their role in Russian spiritual traditions. As Dementyev (2023) observes,

"Speech of a psychic in trance, addressed to "higher powers" - incantations, etc., sometimes in a special language (native for a non-Russian psychic, Sanskrit or a special secret (non-existent?) language). For obvious reasons these spells are of great interest to a part of the audience, they are written out, posted on the Internet, learned, discussed." (Dementyev, 2023: 12).

The show also highlights regional variations in mystical practices, showcasing the diversity of Russia's spiritual landscape. Contestants from different parts of the country bring their unique traditions and perspectives, enriching the narrative and broadening viewers' understanding of Russian mysticism (Fedotov, 1948).

This regional diversity is celebrated and respected, reflecting a broader trend of cultural appreciation and preservation.

In summary, the high production values and thoughtful integration of Slavic magic and cultural elements are key factors in the success of "Psychic Challenge." These elements create a compelling and authentic viewing experience that resonates with Russian-speaking audiences, drawing on their deep-seated spiritual traditions and cultural identity. Through its polished presentation and cultural authenticity, the show not only entertains but also fosters a deeper appreciation for Russia's mystical heritage (Mcintosh, 2022).

Integration of Slavic Magic and Local Cultural Elements

One of the most distinctive aspects of "Psychic Challenge" is its incorporation of Slavic magic and local cultural elements. This integration not only enriches the content of the show but also reinforces its cultural resonance with Russian-speaking audiences.

Traditional Rituals and Symbols

The show frequently features traditional Slavic rituals and symbols, which are deeply embedded in Russian cultural heritage (see Cvetkovic, 2021; Dixon-Kennedy, 1998; Helvin, 2019; and Mcintosh, 2022). These elements include the use of talismans, divination methods such as tarot and rune readings, and rituals involving natural elements like fire and water (see Propp, 2012). By showcasing these practices, "Psychic Challenge" taps into a sense of national identity and cultural pride.

Local Legends and Folklore

Episodes often draw on local legends and folklore, bringing to life the rich tapestry of Russian mythological traditions (see Cvetkovic, 2021; Dixon-Kennedy, 1998). Contestants might be asked to solve mysteries related to historical events, haunted locations, or mythical creatures from Slavic mythology. This use of folklore not only entertains but also educates viewers about their cultural heritage, fostering a deeper connection to the content.

Cultural Authenticity and Relatability

The inclusion of local cultural elements enhances the authenticity and relatability of the show. Viewers see their own traditions and beliefs reflected in the challenges and narratives, making the show more engaging and meaningful. This cultural authenticity is crucial for building a loyal and enthusiastic audience (Turner, 2010a: 22).

Community and Identity

By integrating Slavic magic and local cultural elements, "Psychic Challenge" also fosters a sense of community and shared identity among its viewers. The show provides a platform for the celebration of Russian spiritual traditions and creates a space where viewers can explore and validate their interest in the mystical and supernatural. This communal aspect is an important factor in the show's enduring popularity.

In conclusion, the high-value production elements and the thoughtful integration of Slavic magic and local

cultural traditions are key to the success of "Psychic Challenge." These aspects not only enhance the visual and emotional appeal of the show but also resonate deeply with the cultural and spiritual sensibilities of Russian-speaking audiences. By examining these production elements, we gain a deeper understanding of the factors that contribute to the show's widespread appeal and cultural significance (Turner, 2010a: 24).

Chapter 4: Cultural Imports

Influence of European and American Culture on Russian Television Industry

The landscape of Russian-speaking television industry has been significantly shaped by the influx of European and American cultural imports (Chalaby, 2012, 2015). This influence is evident in various genres, formats, and thematic elements that have been adapted and localized for Russian-speaking audiences. "Psychic Challenge" is a prime example of how global cultural trends have been seamlessly integrated into Russian television industry, creating a unique hybrid that resonates with local sensibilities.

One notable aspect of this cultural import is the adoption of the scripted reality TV format, which gained immense popularity in the United States and Europe before making its way to Russian-speaking space (Chalaby, 2012, 2015). Shows like "Survivor" and "Big Brother" introduced the concept of competitive reality television, where participants undergo various challenges while being closely monitored by cameras. "Psychic Challenge" employs a similar format, but with a focus on supernatural abilities, thereby catering to the Russian fascination with mysticism and the paranormal.

The influence of European and American television is also apparent in the production values and storytelling techniques used in "Psychic Challenge." High-definition cinematography, sophisticated editing, and dramatic music scores are all elements borrowed from Western television, enhancing the show's appeal and making it competitive on a global scale.

Examples of Character Archetypes

Character archetypes from European and American popular culture have also found their way into Russian television, including "Psychic Challenge." These archetypes serve as familiar touchstones for audiences, bridging cultural gaps and making the show more accessible and engaging.

The Addams Family

The Addams Family (Figure 1), an iconic representation of the macabre and the supernatural in American pop culture, provides a template for characters in "Psychic Challenge" (Sonnenfeld, 1991; Wednesday, 2022). The quirky and eccentric personalities of the Addams Family members—each with their own unique abilities and idiosyncrasies—mirror the diverse contestants on "Psychic Challenge." This parallel draws viewers in, offering a sense of familiarity and continuity with global media traditions.

Figure 1. A young medium and her mother are dressed as Wednesday and Morticia Addams, respectively.
Source: TNT-online.ru

Vampires

Vampires, as depicted in Western literature and film, are another archetype that resonates with Russian-speaking audiences. Shows like "Buffy the Vampire Slayer" (1997-2003) and "True Blood" (2008-2014) have popularized the figure of the vampire, imbuing it with themes of immortality, power, and forbidden knowledge (Buffy the Vampire Slayer, 1997-2003; True Blood, 2008-2014). "Psychic Challenge" incorporates these themes, presenting contestants who exhibit otherworldly skills and knowledge, thereby tapping into the same allure that vampires hold in Western media.

These examples highlight how "Psychic Challenge" leverages familiar archetypes from European

and American culture, enriching its narrative and making it more compelling for a diverse audience.

Voodoo with Dolls

Incorporating elements of Voodoo, particularly the use of dolls (Figure 2), "Psychic Challenge" taps into the archetype of the Shadow. This archetype embodies the darker aspects of the human psyche, which the practice of Voodoo often symbolizes in popular culture. Contestants using Voodoo dolls represent the ability to manipulate external circumstances through symbolic acts, connecting with the deep-seated human belief in sympathetic magic — the idea that one can influence something based on its symbolic connection (Alvarado, 2009). This aspect of the show stirs both intrigue and unease, reflecting the viewers' fascination with and fear of the power of the occult.

Figure 2. One of the contestants of "Psychic Challenge: The Rematch" with her ritual doll.
Source: TNT-online.ru

Warlocks or Black Magicians (Чернокнижники)

The archetype of the Warlock or Black Magician, referred to in Russian cultural context as "чернокнижники" (chernoknizhniki), represents a profound engagement with the dark arts. These figures are often portrayed as harnessing supernatural powers for personal gain, crossing moral boundaries and defying societal norms. Their presence in the show introduces ethical questions about the use of mystical powers, challenging viewers to reflect on the nature of good and evil. This archetype also explores themes of forbidden knowledge and the consequences of its pursuit (Connolly, 2015; De Mattos Frisvold, 2014; Horne, 2021).

Chapter 5: Archetypes and Symbolism

Discussion of Jungian and Cultural Archetypes in the Show

"Psychic Challenge" draws heavily on Jungian archetypes, which are universal symbols and themes present in the collective unconscious, as proposed by Carl Jung (2014). These archetypes resonate deeply with audiences, evoking a sense of shared human experience and tapping into fundamental psychological patterns.

The Hero

One of the central archetypes in "Psychic Challenge" is the Hero. Contestants on the show embark on a journey filled with trials and challenges, mirroring the Hero's Journey as described by Joseph Campbell (2020). This archetypal narrative involves the Hero stepping out of their ordinary world, facing and overcoming various obstacles, and ultimately achieving a transformative victory. Viewers identify with the Hero's struggles and triumphs, which enhances their

emotional engagement with the show (Campbell, 2020).

The Sage

The Sage archetype, representing wisdom and knowledge, is embodied by the show's judges and expert commentators. These figures provide guidance, insight, and often serve as mentors to the contestants. Their presence adds a layer of authority and credibility to the show, making the exploration of psychic phenomena more grounded and intellectually stimulating (Jung, 2010, 2014).

The Saboteur, or Trickster

The Trickster archetype is represented by contestants who challenge the status quo and introduce elements of unpredictability and chaos (Jung, 2010). These individuals often possess a sharp wit and a playful nature, which keeps the audience engaged and on their toes. The Trickster disrupts the conventional flow of the show, bringing in an element of surprise and questioning established norms. This archetype embodies the spirit of mischief and the breaking of boundaries, often revealing deeper truths through their actions.

The Spirit, or Medium

The Medium archetype (Figure 3) is central to "Psychic Challenge," where contestants often claim to communicate with spirits or channel otherworldly entities. This archetype represents the bridge between the physical and spiritual realms, providing insight and guidance from beyond. The Medium's role taps into the human fascination with life after death and the desire to connect with loved ones who have passed on. This archetype resonates deeply with viewers seeking comfort and understanding about the afterlife (Baker, 2022; De Mattos Frisvold, 2014; Horne, 2021).

Figure 3. A medium from "Psychic Challenge: Battle of the Strongest" performing a ritual on the show using fire, his attributes, and a skull.

Source: TNT-online.ru

The Shaman

The Shaman archetype is embodied by contestants who perform rituals and ceremonies to invoke spiritual power and healing. These individuals often draw on traditional practices and ancient wisdom, positioning themselves as intermediaries between the natural and supernatural worlds. The Shaman's role in the show highlights the importance of spiritual guidance and the quest for inner harmony, reflecting a deep-seated cultural respect for holistic healing practices (Baker, 2022; Horne, 2021).

The Magician

The Magician archetype represents mastery of the unseen forces and the ability to transform reality through will and intention. Contestants who embody this archetype demonstrate remarkable psychic abilities, performing feats that seem to defy natural laws (Connolly, 2015; De Mattos Frisvold, 2014; Horne, 2021). The Magician's presence in the show taps into the archetypal desire for mastery over one's environment and the pursuit of knowledge and power. This archetype is closely associated with themes of transformation, creativity, and the exploration of the unknown (Jung, 2014).

Christian and/or White Magicians

In contrast, the Christian or White Magicians on the show represent the Magician archetype in a positive light, often linked with healing, protection, and the use of magic for the greater good. These characters draw on spiritual practices that are portrayed as aligned with Christian values or the forces of light, embodying the

archetype of the Healer. Their presence offers a redemptive perspective on the use of mystical powers, emphasizing themes of sacrifice, virtue, and spiritual enlightenment (Fedotov, 1948).

The Immature Magician: The Gifted Child

The Gifted Child archetype (Miller, 1981) is seen in younger contestants or those who display raw, unrefined psychic abilities. This archetype represents untapped potential and the promise of future greatness. The Gifted Child often undergoes significant personal growth and development throughout the show, mirroring the audience's own journey of self-discovery and maturation. This archetype appeals to viewers' sense of nostalgia and the recognition of latent abilities within themselves (Miller, 1981).

Representation of Mystical Figures: Elves, Witches, and Fairies

"Psychic Challenge" also features a range of mystical figures that are deeply rooted in both Jungian archetypes and cultural mythology (see Jung, 2010; Jung, 2014). These figures include elves, witches, and fairies, each bringing their own symbolic significance to the show.

Elves

Elves, often associated with nature, magic, and hidden knowledge (Figure 4), appear in the show through contestants who claim to have a deep connection with the natural world and its energies. This representation taps into the archetype of the Wise Old Man or Woman, figures who possess secret wisdom and a profound understanding of the universe (Baskin, 1984; Froud, 1998; The Editors of Faerie Magazine, 2017).

Figure 4. An elf-looking contestant from "Psychic Challenge: Battle of the Strongest" "wisely" chose to award only one point for his opponent's work.

Source: TNT-online.ru

Witches

Witches, embodying both the light and dark aspects of the feminine, are central to the show's exploration of magic and the occult. The archetype of the Witch is multifaceted, representing both the healer and the sorcerer. Contestants who identify with this archetype often perform rituals and spells, showcasing the

duality of creation and destruction inherent in witchcraft (Baskin, 1984; Helvin, 2019).

Mother-Earth: Witch as Mother and Young Woman as Witch

The Mother-Earth archetype is multifaceted, representing both the nurturing, protective aspects of the

witch and the youthful, rebellious energy of the young woman as witch (McGaa, 1990).

Witch as Mother

This aspect of the Mother-Earth archetype is embodied by contestants who exude a nurturing, maternal presence (Jung, 2014; Neumann, 1991). These individuals often focus on healing, protection, and the welfare of others, drawing on their deep connection to nature and ancient wisdom. The Witch as Mother archetype resonates with viewers' need for comfort, security, and unconditional love, embodying the archetypal Great Mother (McGaa, 1990; Neumann, 1991).

Young Woman as Witch

The Young Woman as Witch represents independence, curiosity, and the exploration of personal power (Helvin, 2019). This archetype is embodied by younger contestants who challenge societal norms and embrace their mystical abilities with confidence and flair. The Young Woman as Witch appeals to viewers' desire for self-empowerment and the breaking of traditional constraints, symbolizing the archetypal journey towards self-actualization (Baskin, 1984).

Fairies

Fairies, symbolizing enchantment, trickery, and the blurring of reality and fantasy, are represented by contestants who engage in activities that challenge the boundaries of the ordinary world. This archetype resonates with viewers' fascination with the mysterious and the unknown, enhancing the show's magical allure (see Baskin, 1984, see also Froud, 1998; The Editors of *Faerie Magazine*, 2017).

By incorporating these mystical figures, "Psychic Challenge" taps into deep-seated cultural and psychological archetypes, making the show not only entertaining but also symbolically rich and resonant.

In conclusion, the exploration of Jungian (2014) archetypes in "Psychic Challenge" adds depth and complexity to the show's narrative. By engaging with these universal symbols and themes, the show resonates with viewers on a profound psychological level, enhancing its appeal and cultural significance (Jung, 2014).

Chapter 6: Subcultures and Alternative Lifestyles

The Resurgence of Gothic, Emo, and Other Subcultures in Russian-speaking space

In recent years, there has been a notable resurgence of alternative subcultures in Russia, including gothic and emo. These subcultures, characterized by their distinct aesthetics, music, and lifestyles, have found new expression and visibility in contemporary Russian-speaking and cultural space. "Psychic Challenge" plays a significant role in this resurgence by

providing a platform for the exploration and validation of alternative identities.

Gothic Subculture

The gothic subculture, with its emphasis on dark aesthetics, romanticism, and a fascination with the macabre, aligns closely with the themes of "Psychic Challenge" (see Crow, 1991; Wright and Townshend, 2015).

Contestants who identify with the gothic subculture often bring elements of this aesthetic to the show, through their attire, makeup, and performances. This visual and thematic alignment helps attract gothic viewers, who see their own interests and values reflected on screen.

Emo Subculture

Similarly, the emo subculture, known for its emotional expressiveness and introspective themes, finds resonance in the narratives of "Psychic Challenge." The show's focus on personal stories, emotional journeys, and the exploration of inner struggles appeals to emo audiences. Contestants who openly share their vulnerabilities and emotional experiences create a sense of connection and authenticity that resonates with the emo community (Fathallah, 2020).

Tattoo and Metal Subcultures

"Psychic Challenge" also engages with various subcultures, including those associated with tattoos and metal music, each carrying their distinct symbolic meanings.

- **Tattoo Subculture:** Tattoos often serve as symbols of identity, experiences, and beliefs. Contestants with visible tattoos bring the archetype of the Rebel into the show, embodying themes of non-conformity and personal expression. Tattoos can also be symbolic of rites of passage, marking significant transformations or commitments to particular paths or communities (see Krutak L and Deter-Wolf, 2020; Mifflin, 2013; Sanders, 1989; and Velliquette et. al., 1998).

- **Metal Subculture:** The metal subculture, known for its intense and often dark aesthetic, aligns with the archetype of the Outcast (Figure 5). This subculture emphasizes themes of alienation, rebellion, and exploration of the shadow side of human nature. Participants from this subculture might bring a different energy to the show, resonating with viewers who feel marginalized or misunderstood. The music and imagery associated with this group enhance the show's exploration of darker themes, adding depth and complexity to its cultural narrative (Mudrian, 2009; Popoff et. al., 2023).

Figure 5. A psychic from "Psychic Challenge: Battle of the Strongest" exudes a subcultural vibe with her leather jacket and rose tattoo on her neck. She also embodies the role of the Outcast, as she is currently last in the tournament standings.

Source: TNT-online.ru

By weaving these diverse elements into its narrative, "Psychic Challenge" not only entertains but also engages with deep cultural and psychological archetypes. It provides a platform for the exploration of a broad spectrum of human experiences and beliefs, reflected in the varied archetypes and subcultures it portrays. This diversity enriches the show's appeal and facilitates a wider cultural dialogue about the nature of power, identity, and transformation (Turner, 2010b: 37–38).

Role of Alternative Lifestyles and Creative Communities in Modern Russian Entertainment

Alternative lifestyles and creative communities play a crucial role in shaping modern Russian-speaking entertainment. Shows like "Psychic Challenge" provide a space where diverse identities and unconventional beliefs can be explored and celebrated.

Creative Expression and Identity

For many participants and viewers, "Psychic Challenge" is more than just a television show; it is a medium for creative expression and the exploration of personal identity. The show's inclusive approach allows for the representation of various subcultures, fostering a sense of belonging and acceptance among viewers who might feel marginalized in mainstream society (Fathallah, 2020; Mifflin, 2013; Mudrian, 2009; Popoff et. al., 2023).

Community and Support

The show also helps build supportive communities around shared interests in the supernatural and the mystical. Online forums, fan clubs, and social media groups dedicated to "Psychic Challenge" provide spaces for fans to connect, share experiences, and support one another. These communities often extend beyond the show, contributing to a broader network of alternative lifestyles and creative expressions in Russia.

In summary, the resurgence of gothic, emo, and other subcultures in Russian-speaking and cultural

space is closely linked to the cultural impact of "Psychic Challenge." The show provides a platform for alternative lifestyles and creative communities, enriching modern Russian-speaking entertainment and fostering a sense of inclusivity and community.

Chapter 7: Community Building

Comparison to Historical Communities Like the Theosophical Society, Freemasons, and Illuminati

The community-building aspect of "Psychic Challenge" can be compared to historical esoteric communities such as the Theosophical Society (see Blavatsky, 1977, and Blavatskyhouse, n.d.; see also The Theosophical Society in Australia, n.d., and Theosophy World, n.d.), Freemasons (Bauer, 2016), and Illuminati (see Marrs, 2018). These groups, though varied in their beliefs and practices, share common goals of seeking hidden knowledge, personal transformation, and the creation of supportive networks.

Theosophical Society

Founded by Helena Blavatskaya in the late 19th century, the Theosophical Society (Blavatsky, 1977) aimed to explore universal spiritual truths and promote the study of comparative religion, philosophy, and science (see Blavatsky, 1977, and Blavatskyhouse, n.d.; see also The Theosophical Society in Australia, n.d., and Theosophy World, n.d.). Like the Theosophical Society, "Psychic Challenge" fosters an environment where diverse spiritual beliefs are explored and validated. The show's emphasis on personal growth and the pursuit of hidden knowledge mirrors the Society's objectives, creating a modern-day parallel in the realm of popular media.

Freemasons

The Freemasons, a fraternal organization with roots in medieval stonemasonry, emphasize moral and spiritual development through symbolic rituals and teachings (Bauer, 2016; see also Karg and Young,

2009; Ridley, 2011). "Psychic Challenge" similarly uses rituals and symbolic challenges to test and showcase the abilities of its contestants. This ritualistic element helps build a sense of community among participants and viewers, who share a collective journey of discovery and enlightenment.

Illuminati

The Illuminati, often shrouded in mystery and conspiracy theories, represents a pursuit of enlightenment and the uncovering of hidden truths (Marrs, 2018). While "Psychic Challenge" does not delve into conspiracy theories, it shares the Illuminati's emphasis on revealing hidden knowledge and exploring the unknown. This shared pursuit creates a sense of camaraderie and collective curiosity among viewers.

The Creation of Modern Communities Around the Show and Its Impact on Viewers

"Psychic Challenge" has given rise to modern communities that are deeply engaged with the show's content and themes. These communities, both online and offline, play a significant role in the show's impact on viewers.

Online Communities

The rise of social media and online forums has enabled fans of "Psychic Challenge" to connect and form vibrant communities. Platforms like VKontakte, Instagram, and specialized forums host discussions, fan art, and speculations about the show's content and contestants (see Alexander Sheps Official Group, n.d.; Psychic Challenge, n.d.; The Psychic Challenge Convention, n.d.; The Secret Chat Room of the Psychic Challenge, n.d.). These online interactions enhance the viewers' experience by allowing them to share theories, insights, and emotional responses to each episode, fostering a deeper connection with the show and its characters.

Offline Communities

Offline, "Psychic Challenge" has inspired meetups, conventions, and viewing parties, where fans gather to watch episodes together, participate in themed activities, and engage in psychic readings and discussions (Psychic Challenge, n.d.; The Psychic Challenge Convention, n.d.).

These gatherings not only enhance the communal experience but also allow fans to express their identities and beliefs in supportive, like-minded groups. This aspect of community building is crucial, particularly for individuals who seek acceptance of their interests in mysticism and the supernatural, which might otherwise be marginalized (Meeting with Psychic Challenge season 24 contestant Samantha Adam, 2024; Public Talk with TNT Psychics in St. Petersburg, 2024; The Evening Barnaul, 2023; Zelenograd's Infoportal, 2024).

Impact on Viewers

The community aspect of "Psychic Challenge" significantly impacts its viewers by providing a sense of belonging and identity (Turner, 2010b: 43). For many, the show offers a gateway into exploring their own psychic abilities or interests in the supernatural. It validates their experiences and encourages them to connect with others who share similar interests, thus mitigating the isolation that can come from holding unconventional beliefs.

Furthermore, these communities often act as support networks, offering emotional support and encouragement. This is particularly important in a show that deals with the esoteric and supernatural, where participants and viewers often explore personal and sometimes vulnerable aspects of their lives.

Cultural and Social Implications

The community-building around "Psychic Challenge" also has broader cultural and social implications. By bringing together diverse groups of people, the show plays a role in the cultural integration of subcultures within mainstream Russian-speaking society. It challenges stereotypes and prejudices about alternative lifestyles and beliefs, promoting a more inclusive understanding of cultural diversity.

Moreover, these communities often initiate discussions about spiritual and philosophical questions, contributing to a cultural discourse that goes beyond mere entertainment. The show becomes a medium through which contemporary Russian-speaking society can engage with questions about the nature of reality, the existence of the supernatural, and the human capacity for psychic phenomena.

In conclusion, "Psychic Challenge" does more than entertain; it fosters a sense of community and belonging among viewers who are drawn to its mystical and supernatural themes. By comparing these modern communities to historical esoteric societies, we can see a continuing thread of human curiosity and the need for connection through shared mystical and occult interests. The show's ability to bring people together, therefore, is not just a testament to its entertainment value but also to its role in shaping cultural and social landscapes.

Chapter 8: Conclusion

Influence on Cultural and Spiritual Practices

The show also influences broader cultural and spiritual practices in Russian-speaking and cultural space. By popularizing various aspects of mysticism and the paranormal, "Psychic Challenge" encourages viewers to explore these realms in their own lives. This exploration can manifest in increased participation in activities such as tarot reading, meditation, and other spiritual practices. The normalization of these practices through mainstream media helps integrate them into everyday life, contributing to a broader cultural shift towards acceptance of diverse spiritual beliefs (Cvetkovic, 2021; Helvin, 2019).

Educational and Informative Role

"Psychic Challenge" serves an educational role by exposing viewers to a wide range of psychic phenomena and spiritual traditions. The expert commentary and diverse challenges presented in the show provide viewers with knowledge and insights into different mystical practices. This educational aspect helps demystify the supernatural, making it more approachable and understandable for the general public.

Community Support and Mental Health

The sense of community fostered by "Psychic Challenge" can also have positive implications for mental health. Being part of a supportive network where individuals share similar interests and beliefs can alleviate feelings of isolation and provide emotional

support. The communal aspect of the show encourages viewers to connect with like-minded individuals, fostering friendships and social bonds that contribute to overall well-being.

Conclusion

"Psychic Challenge" is not just a television show; it is a cultural phenomenon that reflects and shapes contemporary Russian-speaking society. Through its high-value production, integration of local cultural elements, and engagement with global cultural trends, the show resonates deeply with its audience. The exploration of Jungian archetypes (Jung, 2010; Jung, 2014) and mystical figures adds symbolic richness, while the validation of alternative subcultures and lifestyles creates a platform for diverse identities to be celebrated.

The community-building aspect of "Psychic Challenge" is particularly significant. The show has given rise to modern communities that mirror historical esoteric groups in their pursuit of hidden knowledge and spiritual enlightenment. These communities, both online and offline, provide spaces for engagement, support, and personal growth, significantly impacting viewers' lives and contributing to the show's enduring popularity (Meeting with Psychic Challenge season 24 contestant Samantha Adam, 2024; Psychic Challenge, n.d.; Public Talk with TNT Psychics in St. Petersburg, 2024; The Psychic Challenge Convention, n.d.).

By examining the historical context, cultural imports, archetypes, subcultures, and community-building aspects of "Psychic Challenge," this study provides a comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to its success. The show's ability to resonate with deep-seated cultural and psychological themes, while also fostering a sense of community and belonging, highlights its profound impact on modern Russian-speaking culture and media space.

References:

- Alexander Sheps Official Group (n.d.) Official Group VK. Available at: <https://vk.com/club42806518> (accessed 25 May 2024).
- Alvarado D (2009) *Voodoo Dolls In Magick And Ritual*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Andreyev A (2014) *The Myth of the Masters Revived: The Occult Lives of Nikolai and Elena Roerich*. Leiden: Brill Academic Publishers.
- Baker MT (2022) *The Way of the Mystic-Wizard: A Guidebook for Creating a Nondual Shamanic Spiritual Practice*. La Vergne, Tennessee: Lightning Source.
- Baskin L (1984) *Imps, Demons, Hobgoblins, Witches, Fairies & Elves*. New York: Pantheon Books.
- Bauer C (2016) *The Freemasons: The Mysterious Roots of Freemasonry: The Hidden Truths of History's Most Mysterious Secret Society*. Rochester: Maplewood Publishing.
- Blavatsky HP (1977) *The Secret Doctrine: The Synthesis of Science, Religion, and Philosophy*. California: Theosophical University Press.
- Blavatsky HP (1997) *Isis Unveiled: Secrets of the Ancient Wisdom Tradition, Madame Blavatsky's First Work*. Wheaton, Illinois: Quest Books.
- Blavatskyhouse (n.d.) *The Theosophical Society Point Loma*. Available at: <https://blavatskyhouse.org/> (accessed 25 May 2024).
- Buffy the Vampire Slayer (1997-2003) TV Series. Los Angeles, California: Mutant Enemy Productions.
- Campbell J (2020) *The Hero with a Thousand Faces*. New York: Joseph Campbell Foundation.
- Chalaby JK (2012) At the origin of a global industry: The TV format trade as an Anglo-American invention. *Media, Culture & Society* 34(1): 36-52.
- Chalaby JK (2015) *Drama without Drama: The Late Rise of Scripted TV Formats*. *Television & New Media* 17(1): 3-20.
- Connolly S (2015) *The Complete Book of Demonolatry*. Arvada: DB Publishing.
- Crow CL (1991) *American Gothic: An Anthology From Salem Witchcraft to H. P. Lovecraft*. Hoboken, New Jersey: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Cvetkovic S (2021) *Slavic Traditions & Mythology*. Independently Published.
- De Mattos Frisvold N (2014) *Craft of the Untamed: An Inspired Vision of Traditional Witchcraft*. Oxford: Mandrake of Oxford.
- Dementyev VV (2023) "Psychic Discourse" and its Dominants (on the Material of the TV Show "Psychic Challenge"). *Communication Studies* 10(1): 7-22.
- Dixon-Kennedy M (1998) *Encyclopedia of Russian and Slavic Myth and Legend*. New York: ABC-CLIO.
- Fathallah JM (2020) *Emo. How Fans Defined a Subculture*. Iowa: University of Iowa Press.
- Fedotov GP (1948) *Treasury of Russian Spirituality*. New York: Sheed & Ward.
- Froud B (1998) *Good Faeries/Bad Faeries*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Gurdjieff GI (1950) *An objectively impartial criticism of the life of man, or, Beelzebub's tales to his grandson*. San Diego, California: Harcourt.
- Gurdjieff GI (1991) *Meetings with Remarkable Men*. London: Penguin Publishing Group.
- Helvin N (2019) *Slavic Witchcraft: Old World Conjuring Spells and Folklore*. Merrimac: Destiny Books.
- Horne RJ (2021) *Folk Witchcraft: A Guide to Lore, Land, and the Familiar Spirit for the Solitary Practitioner*. Independently Published.
- Jung CG (2010) *Four Archetypes*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Jung CG (2014) *The Archetypes and the Collective Unconscious*. London: Taylor & Francis Group.
- Karg B and Young JK (2009) *101 Secrets of the Freemasons: The Truth Behind the World's Most Mysterious Society*. Stoughton, Massachusetts: Adams Media.
- Krutak L and Deter-Wolf A (2020) *Ancient Ink: The Archaeology of Tattooing*. Seattle, Washington: University of Washington Press.
- Lachman G (2006) *In Search of P. D. Ouspensky: The Genius in the Shadow of Gurdjieff*. Wheaton, Illinois: Quest Books.

32. Lipsey R (2019) *Gurdjieff reconsidered: the life, the teachings, the legacy*. Boulder: Boulder Shambhala Center.
33. Marrs J (2018) *Illuminati Societatea secreta care a deturnat intreaga lume*. Bucharest: In Extensio.
34. McGaa E (1990) *Mother Earth spirituality: Native American paths to healing ourselves and our world*. San Francisco: Harper & Row.
35. Mcintosh C (2022) *Occult Russia: Pagan, Esoteric, and Mystical Traditions*. Rochester: Inner Traditions International.
36. Mediascope (n.d.) Ratings. Available at: <https://mediascope.net/data/> (accessed 25 May 2024).
37. Meeting with Psychic Challenge season 24 contestant Samantha Adam (2024) *White Clouds*. Available at: <https://white-clouds.ru/events/vstrecha-s-uchastnitsey-24-sezona-bitvy-ekstrasensov-samantoy-adam/> (accessed 25 May 2024).
38. Mifflin M (2013) *Bodies of Subversion: A Secret History of Women and Tattoo*. Brooklyn, New York: powerHouse Books.
39. Miller A (1981) *The drama of the gifted child*. New York: Basic Books.
40. Mokhov S (2016) Taking the Spell off of Death: Media as Mourning Ritual in Russia's Psychic Challenge. *Laboratorium* 8(2): 32–49.
41. Mudrian A (2009) *Precious Metal*. New York: Hachette Books.
42. Neumann E (1991) *The Great Mother: An Analysis of the Archetype*. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
43. Popoff M, Dome M, Reesman B and Kilmister L (2023) *The Art of Metal: Five Decades of Heavy Metal Album Covers, Posters, T-shirts, and More*. Atglen, Pennsylvania: Schiffer.
44. Propp V (1968) *Morphology of the Folktale*. Texas: University of Texas Press.
45. Propp V (1984) *The Theory and History of Folklore*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
46. Propp VY (2012) *Russian Folktale*. Detroit: Wayne State University Press.
47. Psychic Challenge (n.d.). Fan community in Telegram. Available at: https://t.me/bitva_extrasensi (accessed 25 May 2024).
48. Public Talk with TNT Psychics in St. Petersburg (2024) *Vokzal 1853*. Timepad. Available at: <https://gpm-rtv-spb.timepad.ru/event/2800397/> (accessed 25 May 2024).
49. Ridley JG (2011) *The Freemasons: A History of the World's Most Powerful Secret Society*. New York: Arcade Publishing.
50. Roerich N (2017a) *Adamant*. New York: Nicholas Roerich Museum.
51. Roerich N (2017b) *Heart of Asia*. New York: Nicholas Roerich Museum.
52. Roerich N (2017c) *Shambhala*. New York: Nicholas Roerich Museum.
53. Sanders C (1989) *Customizing the body the art and culture of tattooing*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
54. Sonnenfeld B (1991) *Addams Family*. Film. Hollywood: Paramount Pictures.
55. The Editors of Faerie Magazine (2017) *The Faerie Handbook: An Enchanting Compendium of Literature, Lore, Art, Recipes, and Projects*. New York: Harper Design.
56. The Evening Barnaul (2023) The filming of "Battle of the Psychics" took place in a Barnaul courtyard. Available at: <https://barnaul.press/news/v-barnaulskom-dvore-proshli-syemki-bitvy-ekstrasensov.html> (accessed 25 May 2024).
57. The Psychic Challenge Convention (n.d.) TikTok Search Results. Available at: <https://www.tiktok.com/discover/сходка-битвы-экстрасенсов> (accessed 25 May 2024).
58. The Secret Chat Room of the Psychic Challenge (n.d.) VK Community. Available at: <https://vk.com/club42806518> (accessed 25 May 2024).
59. The Theosophical Society in Australia (n.d.) H.P. Blavatsky and Her Writings. Available at: <https://theosophicalsociety.org.au/statics/h-p-blavatsky-and-her-writings> (accessed 25 May 2024).
60. Theosophy World (n.d.) The Blavatsky Institute of Canada. Available at: <https://theosophy.world/encyclopedia/blavatsky-institute-canada> (accessed 25 May 2024).
61. *True Blood* (2008-2014) TV Series. New York: HBO Entertainment.
62. Turner G (2010a) Ordinary people: celebrity, tabloid culture and the function of the media. In *Ordinary People and the Media: The Demotic Turn*. London: SAGE Publications, pp. 12-32.
63. Turner G (2010b) Reality TV and the Construction of Cultural Identities. In *Ordinary People and the Media: The Demotic Turn*. London: SAGE Publications, pp. 33-70.
64. Velliquette AM, Murray JB and Creyer EH (1998) The Tattoo Renaissance: an Ethnographic Account of Symbolic Consumer Behavior", in *Advances in Consumer Research* (25). Provo, UT: Association for Consumer Research, pp. 461-467.
65. *Wednesday* (2022) TV Series. Los Angeles, California: Netflix.
66. Wright A and Townshend D (2015) *Romantic Gothic: An Edinburgh Companion*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
67. Zelenograd's Infoportal (2024) The "Psychic Challenge" filming took place in the Serednikovo estate. Available at: <https://www.netall.ru/culture/news/1353880.html> (accessed 25 May 2024).